

Effect of Temperature on Ion-Exchange Equilibria in Mixed Solvents: Part I—Alkali-Hydrogen Exchange in Aqueous Acetone on Dowex-50w x-8.

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The equilibrium constants for alkali-hydrogen exchanges on Dowex -50W X-8 (a sulpho-nated copolymer of styrene and divinyl benzene, 8%) in aqueous acetone solutions have been determined at temperatures 25°, 35° and 45°. The equilibrium constants (thermodynamic) have shown an increase with increase in temperature, as well as with acetone percentages. The thermodynamic functions ΔF° , ΔH° and ΔS° have been evaluated for exchanges under study for each mixed solvent system used. The variability of equilibrium constants leading to selectivity changes with temperature in these mixed solvents have been shown to be controlled by entropy (ΔS°), changes, while ΔS° variations are influenced by (a) ion-pair interactions and (b) disturbances in hydration spheres of metal ions. The free energy of exchange (ΔF°) decreases with increase in organic solvent concentration.

THE process of ion exchange, as a rule, involves little evolution or uptake of heat as it is not a chemical reaction. Hence the temperature dependence of ion-exchange equilibria is usually minor; though other processes following ion-exchange may considerably contribute to overall heat change. This temperature dependence of ion exchange equilibria in general is related to the standard enthalpy (ΔH°) changes which accompany the reaction and can be given by the relation—

$$\left(\frac{d \ln K_B^A}{dT} \right)_p = \frac{\Delta H^\circ}{RT^2}$$

where K_B^A is the rational thermodynamic equilibrium constant and ΔH° is the standard enthalpy change for an exchange reaction—

Experimentally this dependence of equilibria on temperature has been studied calorimetrically as heats of exchange, as well as by studying the effect of temperature on selectivity coefficients. The earlier studies¹⁻¹³ in this direction have been carried out in aqueous solutions in which the selectivity dependence on other factors, such as water uptake, ionic strength of the outside solution, resin structure etc. is well understood. But very little is known about heats of exchange in mixed solvents^{14,15}. Recently an attempt has been made in this direction by Gupta, Ghate and Shanker¹⁶ using methanol—water systems. The alcoholic solvents are usually considered to involve ion-pair formation and/or association during exchange and thus complicate matters further. Acetone is a solvent which is much less complicating

in these respects though it is capable of solubilising electrolytes and dissociating them at-least partly. Ion exchange with acetone solutions, therefore resembles exchange of weak aqueous electrolytes with weakly dissociated resins. The presence of water in acetone further affect the equilibria and the rate.

In the present communication, acetone-water mixtures, have been used to study alkali-hydrogen exchange at three temperatures. The selectivity coefficients have been determined as a function of resin composition at three temperatures for aqueous and three acetone-water mixtures (i.e., 10, 30 and 50% on volume to volume basis). The thermodynamic quantities as free energy ΔF° , enthalpy ΔH° and entropy ΔS° for Li^+/H , Na^+/H and K^+/H exchanges have been calculated from equilibrium data and discussed.

Experimental

Resin, solvents and chemicals: The exchanger used in the present studies was Dowex-50-X 8 in hydrogen form (-20+50 BSS mesh size). It was conditioned by a double cycle (H-Na) of exhaustion and regeneration using 2M NaCl and HCl solutions and was finally converted to hydrogen form. It was then washed with deionised water till free from acidity. It was air dried ($\sim 30^\circ$) before storing in air-tight amber coloured bottles.

The stock electrolyte solutions (0.5M) were prepared by using B.D.H., Analar nitrates of lithium, sodium and potassium. To prepare solutions for exchange studies these were suitably diluted with distilled water and acetone (B.D.H., Analar) to give 0, 10, 30 and 50% (volume/volume) aqueous acetone

solutions of 0.1M strength with respect to the metal ions under study.

Equilibrium studies

All equilibrium studies were carried out by using 0.5 g. of the air-dried resin each time with 50 ml. of different electrolyte solutions (either aqueous or mixed with acetone) separately in glass stoppered Erlenmeyer flasks. All exchange studies were carried out in a thermostatic bath (controlled with in $\pm 0.1^\circ$) at three different temperatures, namely 25° , 35° , and 45° . The reaction flasks were shaken intermittently during equilibration under thermostatic conditions. A sufficiently good time interval (~ 12 hrs.) was allowed for the attainment of equilibrium in each case.

The solution phase was analysed for the equilibrium exchange by estimating acidity in aliquots (5 ml.) titrimetrically.

The values of selectivity coefficient or apparent equilibrium constant, K_a , defined as below were calculated from the equilibrium data.

$$K_a = \frac{XB_X}{XA_R} \cdot \frac{CA_W}{CB_W}$$

where X terms are equivalent of resinates and C terms are concentrations in aqueous phase.

This expression has been used by Kressman and Kitchener¹⁷ and Bhatnagar^{18,19} *et al* in earlier communications for calculating selectivity coefficients. The rational thermodynamic constants were evaluated (Table 1) from such K_a values at several XB_R values,

TABLE 1—THERMODYNAMIC EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANT AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND SOLVENT COMPOSITION

Temp., °C	ln K			
	0	Acetone, % (v/v) 10	30	50
(A) Li^+/H^+ Exchange				
25	1.22	1.29	1.54	1.88
35	1.83	1.99	2.23	2.58
45	1.95	2.06	2.43	2.78
(B) Na^+/H^+ Exchange				
25	1.25	1.45	1.71	1.96
35	1.31	1.66	1.96	2.40
45	1.45	1.78	2.72	2.61
(C) K^+/H^+ Exchange				
25	1.51	1.69	2.09	2.66
35	1.73	1.96	2.36	2.96
45	1.91	2.12	2.54	3.24

between zero to one by graphical integration using the expression $\ln K = \int_0^1 \ln K_a dXB_R$, given and used by Boyd^{7,8} *et al* in their studies for aqueous systems at different temperatures and also by Gupta, Ghate and Shanker¹⁶ for exchange in aqueous methanol

solvents. The applicability of this equation to mixed solvents is conditional. Thus under the conditions of low ionic strength ($\leq 0.1M$) and of same solvent composition inside and outside the resin phase, the equation can be applied to exchange systems in mixed solvents. For methanol water mixtures Gable and Strobel¹⁵ have shown that solvent uptake is practically the same in the outside and inside solutions when the mole fraction of the organic solvent in the mixture is 0.5 or less. The present studies have been carried out at ionic concentration $\leq 0.1M$ and acetone concentration upto 50% on volume to volume basis. Thus the conditions for satisfactory applicability of the above equation for calculating thermodynamic constants have been maintained in the work.

Discussion

The heats of ion-exchange reactions are usually investigated by studying the effect of temperature on selectivity coefficients. It has been found out from the present studies at different acetone concentrations (Table 1) that in general the thermodynamic equilibrium constants increase with increase in temperature. The plots of $\ln K$ versus $1/T_A^\circ$ are smooth curves (Fig. 1) showing a regular change in K value (which are the measures of the selectivities of ions) with temperature.

Fig. 1

In Li^+/H^+ exchange an increase in entropy and enthalpy has been observed with increase in acetone concentration in outside solution (Table 2). For uni-valent ion-exchange in aqueous systems Boyd^{7,8} *et al* have observed evolution of heat and decrease

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS AT DIFFERENT SOLVENT COMPOSITIONS

Acetone, % v/v	ΔF° Cal./mole (at 35°)	ΔH° Cal./mole	ΔS° Cal./mole/deg (at 35°)
(A) Li^+/H^+ Exchange			
0	-1121	12144	43.0
10	-1220	15972	49.3
30	-1368	13745	48.8
50	-1580	13974	50.4
(B) Na^+/H^+ Exchange			
0	-863	1150	6.5
10	-1019	4238	16.9
30	-1203	5068	20.2
50	-1467	8752	33.0
(C) K^+/H^+ Exchange			
0	-1061	4376	17.5
10	-1200	5388	21.2
30	-1444	5388	22.08
50	-1813	5942	25.04

○ — Li^+
 △ — Na^+
 □ — K^+

in entropy with the uptake of the preferred ion by the exchanger. But in the present case, lithium, being a less preferred ion in its exchange against hydrogen form of the resin, increase in entropy and absorption of heat has been observed. Thus, increase in ΔS° is due to the release of bound water in acetone-water systems, so that the resin imbibes acetone also making the composition of resin and outside solution same with respect to the organic solvent (cf. Gable¹⁵ *et al.*). This effect increases with increasing acetone concentration and hence the increase in ΔS° values. The mixing of the solvent has little, but positive contribution to entropy. Thus our results for Li^+/H^+ exchange in aqueous acetone are in agreement with those of Gupta¹⁶ *et al* for this exchange in aqueous methanol.

Studies for Na^+/H^+ exchanges in aqueous acetone have yielded similar results. Thus, increase in entropy and evolution of heat have been observed in these cases also (Table 2). Though the values for ΔS° are all positive, yet their magnitudes are not in the order of their decreasing hydrated ionic sizes (which are supposed to be the measure of exchange selectivities). This may be attributed to differences in the nature of the reaction in ions under study. The higher values of ΔS° in Li^+/H^+ exchange are indicative of the possibilities of certain other interactions occurring simultaneously with exchange in aqueous acetone solvents. Lithium has tendency to give ion-pair formations of different nature in nonaqueous medium. Its exchange is, therefore, influenced also by interactions other than exchange. The values of ΔS° for Na^+/H^+ and K^+/H^+ exchanges are less than that for Li^+/H^+ exchange and they are in increasing order for the two alkali metal ions as expected on the basis the two alkali metal ions as expected on the basis of their decreasing hydrated ionic sizes. Thus, the side interactions in two ex-

changes are much less than those supposed in Li^+/H^+ exchange.

The positive and rather large values of ΔS° for alkali metal/hydrogen exchanges may be attributed to the disturbances caused by the addition of acetone to aqueous systems in otherwise systematised hydration spheres of these metal ions. Thus, a randomness exists in the system. The positive and large values of ΔS° are indicative of such disturbances in the alkali-metal/hydrogen exchanges in aqueous acetone systems.

The plot of ΔS° versus ΔH° is linear (Fig. 2) and all points for the alkali metal/hydrogen exchange systems fall on the same line showing changes in entropy by changes in enthalpy in all cases. Similar results have been shown for aqueous studies by Soldatov²⁰ *et al.*

Fig. 2
 ○ — Li^+
 △ — Na^+
 □ — K^+

The values of ΔF° for all exchanges involving univalent ions have been shown to be negative and in decreasing order with increasing acetone concentration. Thus free energy of the exchange reaction is decreasing with increase in organic solvent concentration. In other words, the exchange reaction is becoming slower in solutions containing increasing percentages of less polar solvent, i.e., acetone.

The selectivities of these ions, as measured by K , show changes by changing solvent composition with respect to organic component. The selectivity of lithium by-passes that of sodium at 50% acetone and higher temperatures (35° and 45°). This appears to be due to the combined effect of the presence of organic solvent and temperature. Usually less polar organic solvents enhance complex formation or other side-interactions as ion-pair formation^{21,22} etc.; but temperature rise checks them²³. Hence the overall effect, which is an increase in selectivity, is more due to the presence of organic solvent rather than the effect of temperature.

Though for exchanges in aqueous solutions, the enthalpy changes have been supposed to be the controlling factor for selectivities, yet it cannot be so for mixed and partly aqueous solvents. Gupta *et al.* (loc.cit.) have emphasized the importance of entropy changes in selectivity reversals in mixed-solvent systems. The present studies support their conclusions showing the fact that changes in ΔS° are responsible for variation in selectivities of ions. The ΔS° values in their turn are influenced by two factors—(a) ion-pair interactions of some type and (b) disturbances in hydration spheres of metal ions. Both these factors are facilitated by the presence of the organic solvent, i.e., acetone. Hence ion exchange process in aqueous acetone is controlled by entropy variations rather than enthalpy changes in the systems.

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